

**PREVENTION OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN A MODERN
INTERPRETATION**

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***Abstract.** This thesis presents scientific information about the prevention of arterial hypertension in a modern interpretation.*

***Key words:** Arterial hypertension, syndrome, diastolic blood pressure, rest, activity, waking up after sleep.*

**ПРОФИЛАКТИКА АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ
ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ.**

***Аннотация.** В диссертационной работе представлены научные сведения о профилактике артериальной гипертензии в современной интерпретации.*

***Ключевые слова:** Артериальная гипертензия, синдром, диастолическое артериальное давление, отдых, активность, пробуждение после сна.*

Relevance: Arterial hypertension is a syndrome of increased systolic and (or) diastolic blood pressure. To make such a diagnosis, the systolic level should be above 140 mmHg, and diastole should be above 90 mmHg. This condition is observed with repeated measurements, at different times of the day and under different conditions (rest, activity, waking up after sleep).

Hypertension is also called hypertension or essential hypertension. The term "hypertension" was introduced in 1948 by the Soviet scientist GF Lang. Hypertension is one of the most common forms of arterial hypertension. According to statistics, about 30% of the adult population suffers from it, and the probability of developing the pathology increases over the years. With a sharp and significant increase in pressure, an attack called "hypertensive crisis" may occur. This is a dangerous condition that requires immediate medical attention, such as intravenous therapy.

Purpose of the work: Compliance with the recommendations helps to prevent the development of arterial hypertension. If the symptoms of the disease are already present, prevention and a healthy lifestyle will slow down the development:

Aims and objectives of the study: Control your body weight. Excess weight is one of the main triggering factors for the development of hypertension. According to statistics, every kilogram of weight added increases the average blood pressure level by one to two mmHg.

Maintaining a normal body weight through a balanced diet and exercise can help prevent hypertension.

Research materials: Eat right. The diet should be balanced, rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, lean protein and low-fat dairy products. Give preference to lean meat or fish, vegetable oil, low-fat cottage cheese and nuts. Foods rich in potassium and magnesium are especially useful for hypertensive patients - greens, figs, nuts, legumes, beans, raisins. It is important to avoid foods rich in saturated and trans fats, excess salt and sugar.

Give up bad habits. Smoking and alcohol damage blood vessels and increase the risk of heart disease and stroke. Thus, with complete withdrawal from nicotine, the risk of death from heart and vascular diseases is reduced by half. Every cigarette smoked quietly raises blood pressure levels.

Do moderate physical activity. Exercise regularly and move more: it helps to maintain a normal weight, strengthens the cardiovascular system and lowers blood pressure. Try to walk often at a moderate pace and exercise for 20-30 minutes a day (at least 3-4 times a week). Watch for shortness of breath, chest pain, or arrhythmia.

Avoid stressful situations. Excitement, anxiety, fear - all these contribute to a jump in blood pressure. It is impossible to completely protect yourself from stress, so try to respond to it adequately. Avoid overwork and fatigue, alternate mental and physical work.

Summary: Timely treatment of chronic diseases, kidney diseases and organs of the endocrine system. If you have diabetes, monitor your blood sugar levels and avoid sudden fluctuations.

Get enough sleep. Chronic sleep deprivation is associated with the risk of hypertension. To prevent the development of pathology, try to sleep 7-8 hours a day.

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